

Effectivity of Vitamin D in Preventing Breast Cancer and Evaluation of 25(OH)D Examination As A Laboratory Screening Tool

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ABSTRACT

Vitamin D is currently associated with many diseases, not only bone health but also in autoimmune diseases, cancer, and neurological disorders. This study focuses on the mechanism relation vitamin D on breast cancer, especially with regard to estrogen receptor-positive (ER+) and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive (HER 2+) cancers. Therapeutic supplementation is a commonly used approach to increase vitamin D levels. The effects of vitamin D have been investigated in various aspects, including regulation of cell growth and differentiation, apoptosis, intercellular contact, angiogenesis, immune function, as well as interaction with gut microbiota. In this study, the effects of vitamin D on breast cancer and its relationship with serum 25(OH)D levels were also researched. As a result, patients newly diagnosed with breast cancer were found to have low serum 25(OH)D levels. Vitamin D administration has been shown to induce apoptosis in breast cancer cells.

KEYWORDS: Breast Cancer, 25(OH)D, Vitamin D

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INTRODUCTION

Vitamin D is a group of fat soluble, its role in all tissues and cells of the human body is maintaining the balance of calcium and phosphorus. It is obtained in fatty fish or certain fruits, are limited, and from supplements. Vitamin D used to promote bone health to prevent osteoporosis, and its beneficial effects on bone health have primarily been related to its physiological role in calcium homeostasis. In recent years, the field has expanded to describe the extraskelatal effects of vitamin D and their underlying mechanisms. The previous study found that vitamin D is associated with autoimmune diseases, infectious diseases, cardiovascular diseases, cancers and neurological disorders has fuelled speculation about its potential indications.^{1,2} Regardless of its provenance including vitamin D₂ or vitamin D₃, the process of enzymatic hydroxylation in the liver produces 25-hydroxyvitamin D (25(OH)D), which is subsequently converted in the kidney to 25OHD₂ or D₃, known as calcitriol. 25(OH)D roles crucial in regulating the metabolism of calcium and phosphorus from ingested food. It has also

been shown to have anti-cancer effects, affecting several types of cancer, including melanoma, Bbreast cancer (BC) and colorectal cancer (CRC).³

Breast cancer is the most prevalent form of cancer among women worldwide, accounting for 79.7% of diagnosed cases in 2020, with a projected increase anticipated by 2030. In a Geographic variations prevalence of higher incidence in Asia and Europe compared to Africa or Oceania, influenced by factors such as alcohol, lack of physical activity, and limited of screening. The intricacy of breast cancer is characterised by inter-individual variability and the presence of diverse tumour subtypes, underscoring the necessity for a comprehensive review of the current scientific literature. The aetiology of breast cancer remains incompletely elucidated, with two predominant theories being the stochastic theory and the breast cancer stem cell theory. Now research into the mechanisms is ongoing, particularly in relation to estrogen receptor-positive (ER+) and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive (HER2+) cancers, is imperative for the development of

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effective prevention strategies. While some risk factors, such as genetics, age, and breast density, are considered to non-modifiable. for modifiable factor including obesity and lifestyle, present opportunities for intervention in breast cancer prevention. Obesity, can contributes to elevated estrogen levels and accelerated cancer cell growth, while lifestyle choices such as alcohol consumption can increase risk by interfering with biological mechanisms. Notwithstanding the identified factors, uncertainties persist regarding the impact of geographic location, environment including pollution, and other variables on breast cancer development. The intricacies of the disease have spurred the exploration of novel prevention strategies, such as breast self-examination or screening. Furthermore, the investigation into the correlation between breast cancer and vitamin D supplementation holds considerable promise in the pursuit of effective prevention and early intervention strategies. Therapeutic supplementation and food fortification are prevalent approaches to augmenting vitamin D levels. Numerous interventional studies have demonstrated the efficacy of supplementation with vitamin D (either D2 or D3) in a single substantial dose or in divided doses by oral and parenteral routes, leading to varying degrees of increase in serum levels of the respective forms of 25(OH)D. Vitamin D has a variates of important functions, including regulating cell growth and differentiation, cell apoptosis, intercellular contacts, angiogenesis, immune function, and interaction with the gut microbiome. These effects are primarily indirect outcomes of transcriptional and and epigenetic changes,

involving synthesis transcription factors, chromatin modified, microRNAs (miRs) and non-coding RNAs (ncRNAs) through proteins interactions and signalling interference. In addition, vitamin D is a agent to counteract several carcinogenesis and epigenetic changes that increase the expression of tumour genes and decrease the expression of tumour suppressor genes.^{3,4}

METHOD

A systematic review of the literature on effect vitamin D on breast cancer and 25(OH)D tools was conducted using primarily PubMed, MDPI and Cochrane library as a secondary search. Using search engine with keyword “Vitamin D”, “breast cancer”, and “25(OH)D”. Prior to sorting and literature search was restricted to human studies between 2021 to 2025. After the initial hit (N = 16.682 from PubMed, N = 800 from MDPI N = 413 from Cochrane database), we excluded the duplicates from the filter option. This gave us a combined N = 19.910 articles, which were then sorted by the availability of free full texts online. The selection of articles was then conducted in accordance with the established inclusion criteria. This entailed the identification of articles that addressed the relationship between breast cancer and Vitamin D and/or 25(OH)D levels. Additionally, articles encompassing randomized control trial studies conducted between 2021 and 2025 were considered. The final inclusion criterion pertained to research conducted on human subjects.

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RESULT

No.	Title	Years	Authors	p	I	C	O
1.	A Randomized Trial of Calcium Plus Vitamin D Supplementation and Risk of Ductal Carcinoma In Situ of the Breast	2021	Piela. R, <i>et al</i>	Patient in this study is woman that diagnosed Ductal Carcinoma and breast cancer, postmenopouse d.	18.144 patient that given 1000mg calcium + 400 IU vitamin D	18.079 with placebo or not supplementation consumption	The findings suggested that Carcinoma ductal supplementation in postmenopausal women was linked to a reduced risk of developing DCIS, indicating that consistent use of these supplements may offer long-term protective benefits against the condition.
	The high dose of vitamin D supplementation combined with yoga training improve the leukocytes cell survival-related gene expression in breast cancer survivors	2021	Khedmati. Z, <i>et al</i>	The patient with breast cancer that completed radiotherapy and chemotherapy five years before and no had systemic problems.	Ten patient with high dose vitamin D plus yoga and ten patient with low dose vitamin D plus yoga	Ten patient with high dose vitamin D	Participants who received both high and low doses of vitamin D exhibited an upregulation of leukocyte P53 and Bcl2 genes, which role in cell survival. The findings indicated that patients who received a high dose experience a greater increase in the regulation of leukocyte P53 and Bcl2 genes.
	The Effects of Omega-3 Fatty Acids and Vitamin D Supplementation on the Nutritional Status of Women with Breast Cancer in Palestine: An Open-Label Randomized Controlled Trial.	2024	Almassri, <i>et al</i>	Patient is newly diagnosed breast cancer women in Gaza.	24 patients get omega 3 only, 24 patients get vitamin D only, 24 patients get omega-3 plus vitamin D	24 patients no got supplementation	Patients that receiving daily ω3 and weekly Vitamin D supplementation showed improvements in nutritional status, as measured by PG-SGA scores, anthropometric assessments, blood albumin levels, and dietary intake of energy and protein.

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Exploring the synergistic effects of vitamin D and synbiotics on cytokines profile, and treatment response in breast cancer: a pilot randomized clinical trial	2024	Tirgar. A, <i>et al</i>	breast cancer patients receiving neoadjuvant therapy, which took place between 2019 and 2021 in Kerman, Iran.	With vitamin D supplementation	No vitamin supplement	Findings revealed that patients in the vitamin D-supplemented groups experienced a significant increase in serum IL-6 levels, an inflammatory cytokine.
Prevalence and Relevance of Vitamin D Deficiency in Newly Diagnosed Breast Cancer Patients: A Pilot Study	2023	Zemlin, <i>et al</i>	Patient with breast cancer who were checked the serum 25(OH)D level.	Patient with newly diagnosed of breast cancer who were checked 25OHD levels serum with consume vitamin D	Patient with newly diagnosed of breast cancer who were checked 25OHD levels serum with no consume vitamin D	Patients who reported using vitamin D supplements had higher 25(OH)D levels compared to those who did not. Additionally, individuals with moderate vitamin D deficiency were less likely to have triple-negative breast cancer.
Effect of Selected Factors on the Serum 25(OH)D Concentration in Women Treated for Breast Cancer	2024	Radom, <i>et al</i>	Patient with post mastectomy.	Patients that consume vitamin D supplementation	Patients that was not consume vitamin D supplementation	The finding is patient with consume vit D supplementation has serum 25(OH)D level higher than no supplementation

The study from Peila R et al found that Fine-Gray model showed a cumulative reduction in DCIS incidence in the intervention group compared to the control group. After receiving calcium and vitamin D3 intervention treatment, there was a significant risk reduction after the post-intervention period.⁴ Khedmati Z et al in their study gave vitamin D supplements to participants for 12 weeks, found that there was a significant increase in vitamin D, and there was a significant difference in the group that received high-dose vitamin D and the low-dose group. After the intervention, the amount of leukocyte's NF- κ B expression decreased in all groups, but the change was not significant. But, in this study, NF- κ B levels decrease significantly in the high-dose vitamin D group compared with the low-dose group and the high-dose group with yoga.⁵ Almssri et al's study found that omega 3 and vitamin D supplementation significantly increased blood albumin levels. In addition, the

ω 3+VitD group had significantly lower PG-SGA scores and significantly higher weight and BMI levels compared to the control group.⁶ Tirgar et al in their study said that the amount of serum vitamin D increased significantly in the intervention group. There was a reduction in TNF- α levels in the vitamin D group, but the reduction was not statistically significant. In addition, the anti-inflammatory index increased in the Vitamin D+Pro group after treatment.⁹ Research conducted by Zemlin et al stated that serum 25(OH)D values were higher in 18 patients who took vitamin D supplements. There was a significant association in the moderate serum 25(OH)D deficiency group that they were less likely to have triple negative breast cancer, but more likely to have luminal B carcinoma.⁷ Radom et al in their study found that there was an increase in vitamin D concentration after 6 months of intervention. Optimal vitamin D levels were obtained in 14 patients who took vitamin D regularly.⁸

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DISCUSSION

Increased serum calcium levels will reduce the process of cell proliferation and trigger differentiation and cell death. On the other hand, vitamin D works by inhibiting cancer cell proliferation, triggering proapoptotic and anti-angiogenic mechanisms, downregulation of inflammatory mechanisms, and immune response mechanisms.^{4,8} Study observational by Peila research has examined the relationship between serum and dietary calcium, vitamin D, and breast cancer risk, yielding mixed findings. A one-year CaD supplementation trial showed a statistically insignificant reduction in breast cancer risk over a four-year follow-up, with only a few cases of DCIS reported during that time.⁸ In line with other studies revealed that vitamin D reduces the risk of cancer death by reducing tumor growth and increasing the number of tumor-infiltrating cytolytic CD8+ T-cells which is a sign of antitumor response. In breast cancer and anaplastic thyroid cell cancer, 1,25-(OH)2D3 causes G2/M phase arrest which is a consequence of downregulation of CDK2 activity due to the E2F blockade by non-phosphorylated Rb protein. Vitamin D analog will inhibit proliferation through inducing G1 phase arrest in some hematological cancer cells.¹³

Apoptosis is a process maintained by the balance between pro-apoptotic and anti-apoptotic genes. p53 and NF- κ B serve as key regulators of cell survival and can be activated by various stimuli. Yoga practice combined with high-dose vitamin D supplementation led to a significant increase in P53 and Bcl-2 levels, with no notable downregulation of NF- κ B and Bax.⁵ The expression patterns of apoptosis-regulatory genes, including Bcl-2, Bax, and TNF- α , depending on the menstrual cycle. A decreased Bcl-2/Bax ratio in the late and menstruating endometrium increases the susceptibility of glandular cells to apoptosis. In another study, the apoptosis rate and the expression of apoptosis-regulating factors—Bcl-2, Bax, TNF- α , and NF- κ B—were analyzed using molecular biochemical and immunohistochemical techniques in normal proliferative endometrium and across different stages of endometrial hyperplasia and adenocarcinoma.¹⁰ The present study set out to explore the potential of vitamin D in reducing nutritional risk in breast cancer patients. To this end, a group of 50,000 IU of vitamin D was administered to the patients on a weekly basis. The results obtained demonstrated a significant improvement in the patients' nutritional status, as well as in their energy, protein and fat levels. These improvements were also reflected in substantial changes in body weight and BMI levels.⁶ In accordance with the research undertaken by Zemlin (2024), who conducted a study on the correlation between 25(OH)D levels and patient prognosis, as well as lifestyle factors. The findings of this study indicated that patients diagnosed with breast cancer exhibited vitamin D deficiency, as determined by serum 25(OH)D levels.⁷

25(OH)D has been shown to bind to the vitamin D receptor (VDR), a hormone receptor located in the cell nucleus. This interaction alters gene transcription, leading to the activation of some genes and the suppression of others. It also plays a key role in promoting calcium and phosphorus absorption in the intestine. However, the functions of vitamin D go beyond calcium metabolism. VDRs have been identified in various tissues, including the small intestine, colon, T and B lymphocytes, mononuclear cells, brain, and skin. These receptors have been linked to insulin secretion, the regulation of activated T and B lymphocytes, the prevention of inflammatory bowel disease, and the modulation of myocardial contractility. Topical 25(OH)D has proven beneficial in treating psoriasis by reducing redness and flaking associated with the condition. Since keratinocytes in psoriasis exhibit abnormal function, the presence of VDRs in these cells suggests that vitamin D may help regulate their proliferation and differentiation. Another function vitamin D's potential role in cancer therapy. Higher serum levels of 25(OH)D have been associated with improved survival in breast cancer patients. The activation of VDRs by 25(OH)D influences several cellular mechanisms involved in cancer progression, including cell differentiation, proliferation, apoptosis, angiogenesis, and metastatic potential. Additionally, vitamin D has been found to exhibit anti-cancer properties by influencing prostaglandins, which promote tumor growth through increased proliferation and angiogenesis while suppressing cyclooxygenase-2, a key enzyme in prostaglandin synthesis.¹² Higher serum concentrations of the vitamin 25-hydroxyvitamin D3 25(OH)D3 have been shown to be associated with a reduced risk of breast cancer mortality. Indeed, patients with high 25(OH)D levels have been observed to experience approximately half the mortality rate of those with low vitamin D levels.⁸ The present study is not without its limitations, owing to the fact that it combined the provision of Vitamin D supplementation with other supportive therapies, such as yoga or additional supplements. This combination has the potential to introduce bias with regard to the provision of Vitamin D.

CONCLUSION

Vitamin D has been associated with a number of health concerns, including but not limited to bone health, autoimmune diseases, cancer, and neurological disorders. The focus of this discussion will be on the mechanisms of breast cancer, particularly those associated with estrogen receptor positive (ER+) and human epidermal growth factor receptor 2-positive (HER2+) cancers. One common approach to increase vitamin D levels is through supplementation. The mechanisms through which vitamin D exerts its effects on cell growth and differentiation, apoptosis, cell-cell contact, angiogenesis, immune function, and interactions with the gut microbiome have been a focus of research. In this study, the

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effects of vitamin D on breast cancer and its relationship to serum 25(OH)D levels were examined. Patients who were newly diagnosed with breast cancer had low serum 25(OH)D levels. Vitamin D supplementation has been shown to induce apoptosis in breast cancer cells. It has also been demonstrated to enhance nutrition in patients, as measured by BMI. However, the impact of vitamin D supplementation on cell healing was not found to be statistically significant.

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